

On the Hybrid Effect and Fracture Mode of Interlaminated Hybrid Composites

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ABSTRACT

To further the study of the dynamic explanation of the hybrid effect, the hybrid effects of carbon/glass, carbon/Kevlar and Kevlar/glass hybrids have been determined by experiments. The fracture modes of the hybrids as well as related parent composites have been recorded. It is noted that each type of tested composites has its unique fracture mode. The comparison between the theoretical and the experimental hybrid effects has been made. The systematic investigation performed may shine some light on the better understanding of the hybrid effect.

INTRODUCTION

Hybrid composites often behave differently from the composites containing only one type of the component fibers. The state-of-the-art of hybrids has been recently reviewed in (1) and (2). Two aspects of the hybrid behavior are particularly interesting from the view point of basic research: the hybrid effect and modes of fracture.

The term hybrid effect is used to describe the phenomenon that the LE (low elongation) fibers in a hybrid fail at a composite strain higher than that of a composite consisted of the LE fibers only. Since the first observation by Hayashi (3), hybrid effect has been examined rather extensively by researchers, e.g. (4,5,6). Ji, Hsiao and Chou (7) recently provided a dynamic explanation of the hybrid effect. They evaluated the dynamic stress concentration factor in hybrid composites composed of LE and HE (high elongation) fibers. At the fracture of a LE fiber, their model predicts two stress waves propagating along each fiber in the hybrid. The study concludes that hybrid effect always exists in a beneficial manner and the case of the parent LE fiber composite provides the upper bound for the dynamic stress concentration factor in hybrids. This explains the discrepancy between the apparent failure strain of the

LE fiber measured in the parent composite and in the hybrid.

The objective of the present paper is to further the study of dynamic explanation of hybrid effect. To this end, we need to explore answers to the following questions:

1 In the dynamic analysis of (7), only fiber extensional stiffness and density have been taken into account. Whether there are other fiber characteristics which may also contribute to the hybrid effect?

2 Will the hybrids with different combinations of parent fibers all demonstrate the same hybrid effect as revealed by the dynamic analysis?

EXPERIMENTS

Unidirectional fiber composite specimens were prepared for simple tension tests. There were three types of parent composite specimens composed of carbon, Kevlar and glass and three hybrids: carbon/glass, carbon/Kevlar and Kevlar/glass. Each specimen is a laminate composed of three pre-preg tapes impregnated with epoxy. Hybrids have sandwich constructions with the LE fiber layer in the middle. For convenience of designations, three layers laminates are denoted by CCC, GCG, GKG, etc., where C, K, G indicate carbon, Kevlar, glass respectively.

Uniaxial tension experiments were performed on an Instron testing machine at the constant rate of 0.05 cm/min. Three specimens were tested for each type of composites. Typical load-strain curves are shown in Fig. 1 for the parent composites and in Figs. 2-4 for the hybrids.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

HYBRID EFFECT RATIO

Let e_h and e_c denote the failure strains of the LE fiber in the hybrid and the parent composite, respectively. The hybrid effect can be reflected from the parameter termed hybrid effect ratio (8)

$$R_h = (e_h - e_c) / e_c \quad (1)$$

Table 1 gives the measured values of e_h , e_c and R_h for three hybrids.

In (7), the dynamic stress concentration factor K_h was evaluated for a LE fiber immediately adjacent to a fractured LE fiber in an interlaminated hybrid. The dynamic stress concentration factor K_c in a control composite was determined by Hedgepeth (9), as $K_c=1.54$. The hybrid effect ratio of

$$R_h^{\dagger} = (K_c - K_h) / K_h \quad (2)$$

was postulated. Suppose the failure of a hybrid and that of a LE fiber composite are triggered by the failure of a LE fiber. For both types of composites, the condition for unstable fracture of LE fibers is that the dynamic overshoot strain reaches the ultimate tensile strain e_u of the LE fiber. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} e_h &= e_u / K_h \\ e_c &= e_u / K_c \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Substitution of Eqs. (3) into (1), that R_h and R_h^{\dagger} are equivalent in their measurement of the hybrid effect. The R_h^{\dagger} values are shown in Table 2 with the values of R_h .

Table 1 Hybrid Effect Ratio

No.	Hybrid	Specimen	e_c	e_h	R_h %	Mean of R_h %
1	C/G	GCG1	0.013	0.0145	11.5	8.97
		GCG2	0.013	0.0140	7.7	
		GCG3	0.013	0.0140	7.7	
2	C/K	KCK1	0.013	0.0147	13.1	8.73
		KCK2	0.013	0.0141	8.5	
		KCK3	0.013	0.0136	4.6	
3	K/G	GKG1	0.018	0.0186	3.3	1.7
		GKG2	0.018	0.0179	-0.5	
		GKG3	0.018	0.0184	2.2	

The dynamic analysis (7) was performed by assuming a shear lag model containing infinite number of equidistant fibers. This assumption may have contributed to the discrepancy between the R_h^{\dagger} and R_h values. It is also noted that the differences among the R_h values are small relative to the differences among the R_h^{\dagger} values. Furthermore, much stronger hybrid effect are observed in experiments when carbon is used as the LE fiber comparing to the case of Kevlar fiber as the LE fiber.

FRACTURE MODE

The fractured specimens of the parent composites and hybrids are shown in Figs. 5-10. The characteristic features of fracture of all the specimens are summarized in following:

- a, the splitting of specimen into narrow stripes of nearly the same width,
- b, the layer fracturing without splitting,

Fig. 4

- c, the slanted fracture surface,
- d, fracture occurring at both specimen ends,
- e, the scattering in the positions of the fracture of the narrow stripes,
- f, local buckling of the narrow stripes near end-tabs,
- g, delamination.

Fig.11 shows a glass-carbon-glass (G-C-G) sandwich specimen where a teflon film was employed at the layer interface. Bonding between the glass and carbon layers are thus prevented.

Table 2 Theoretical Hybrid Effect Ratio

No.	Hybrid	k_h	R_h^t %	$R_{h,LE/HE}^t$ %
1	C/G	1.490	3.4	39.6
2	C/K	1.505	2.3	
3	K/G	1.495	3.0	3.0

Table 3 Characteristics of Fracture Modes

No.	Specimen	Characteristics of Fracture							Comment
		a	b	c	d	e	f	g	
1	CCC	X			X				
2	KKK	X		X			X		
3	GGG	X				X		X	
4	GCG	X _G	X _C			X _G		X	*
5	KCK	X		X		X			
6	GKG	X _G	X _K	X _K		X		X	
7	G-C-G	X			X _C	X _G			

* The character subscript of the symbol X denotes the layer which has the characteristic feature.

Table 3 shows the fracture characteristics of the seven types of composites given in term of the features a-g as listed above. It is noted that each type of composite has its unique fracture mode. There are no types of composites share the identical fracture mode. The only feature common to all types of composites is the splitting of specimens into narrow stripes, except the carbon layer in carbon/glass hybrid and the Kevlar layer in Kevlar/glass hybrid. The characteristics of fracture of parent composites and their synergistic effects in the hybrids cannot be fully understood until complete characterization of the fibers and the mechanics aspects in the process of fracture can be made.

FRACTURE MODE AND HYBRID EFFECT

In the following, attempts are made to correlate the observed fracture mode with the corresponding measured hybrid effect of the hybrids.

Carbon/Glass Hybrid

The features of Fig.8 suggest that the fracture process may consist of three stages. The carbon layer first fractured along a transverse plane, most likely triggered at the weakest location in the fibers. Delamination between the layers then occurred and followed by the fracture of the glass layers as control composite.

The conclusion that carbon layer fracture precedes delaminations is crucial to the understanding of fracture modes. This conclusion is made based upon the observation that the carbon layer, upon fracturing, does not split into narrow stripes. (see Fig.8) This is possible only if sufficient bounding between the carbon and

Fig. 5 Fracture Mode of Carbon Composite Specimen

Fig. 6 Fracture Mode of Kevlar Composite Specimen

Fig. 7 Fracture Mode of Glass Composite Specimen

Fig. 8 Fracture Mode of Carbon/Glass Hybrid Specimen

Fig. 9 Fracture Mode of Carbon/Kevlar Hybrid Specimen

Fig. 10 Fracture Mode of Kevlar/Glass Hybrid Specimen

Fig. 11 Fracture Mode of Glass-Carbon-Glass Sandwich Specimen

glass layers is maintained during the first stage. On the other hand, the hybrid effect was observed in this hybrid only because delamination took place after the fracture of the carbon layer.

From Fig.5, we can see that the fracture of carbon control composite took place at the both ends of the specimen simultaneously. This is due to that when the stress wave produced by the first fracture of carbon fiber was reflected at the ends of the specimen. If the specimen is considered as fixed rigidly at the ends, then the amplitude of the stress wave at the specimen end was doubled during reflection.

Suppose that, for the carbon control composite, the dynamic stress concentration factors at the specimen ends is K'_c . We can conclude that the hybrid effect ratio of carbon/glass hybrid may be expressed as following:

$$R_{h,c/g}^t = (K'_c - K_h) / K_h \quad (4)$$

As an rough approximation, we simply take $K'_c = 2K_c - 1$. It may cause an exaggerated value predicted by (4) as shown in Table 2.

Carbon/Kevlar Hybrid

The fracture mode of this hybrid is shown in Fig. 9. It can be seen that the fracture mode of the carbon layer here is quite different from that of the carbon layers in the CCC composite or the GCG hybrid. Also, the fracture mode of the Kevlar layer is different from that in the KKK composite or the GKG hybrid. The failure here is characterized by the formation of narrow stripes with varying lengths. No delamination of layers has been detected. Both Kevlar and carbon fibers appeared to fracture at the same strain level, and the sandwich hybrid behaved like a single layer composite. Perhaps, this may be the typical case of so called hybrid. To understand this kind of fracture mode as well as the hybrid effect, further research is necessary.

Kevlar/Glass Hybrid

From Fig. 10, it can be seen that the fracture modes of the Kevlar/glass hybrid and the carbon/glass hybrid are similar. Considering the fracture mode Kevlar control composite is different from that of carbon control composite; the hybrid effect ratio of Kevlar/glass can be calculated by eq.(2), i.e.

$$R_{h,k/g}^t = (K_c - K_h) / K_h \quad (5)$$

The values of $R_{h,c/g}^t$ and $R_{h,k/g}^t$ calculated from eqs. (4) and (5) are shown in Tab. 2.

DISCUSSIONS

1 It is interesting to find out which fiber characteristics control the fracture modes of hybrid and parent composites. As we saw in previous sections, fracture modes are strongly related to the hybrid effect.

2 On the other hand, some fiber characteristics may give remarkable effect on the magnitude of dynamic response in the process of fiber fracture. If these characteristics can be taken into account in the dynamic analysis, it is possible to correlate the experimental and the theoretical hybrid effect ratios in a better manner.

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